

TENSILE PROPERTIES OF METAL-MATRIX COMPOSITES AT HIGH STRAIN RATE AND ELEVATED TEMPERATURES

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ABSTRACT

This paper studies the mechanical properties of a SiC-reinforced Al-matrix composite at elevated temperatures and high strain rate. Tests were performed in a split Hopkinson bar equipped with a furnace to control the temperature of the specimen. The broken samples were examined with a scanning electron microscope to identify the failure micromechanisms. The composites exhibited a remarkable strength retention at high temperatures, and the ambient temperature ductility at high strain rate was better than under quasi-static loading conditions. The fractographic observations indicated that the dominant fracture mechanism changed from reinforcement fracture at low strain rate to ductile failure in the matrix at high strain rate.

1. INTRODUCTION

The reinforcement of metallic matrices (such as Al or Mg alloys) with ceramic particulates or whiskers has led to the development of a new group of composite materials which exhibit very worthwhile properties, especially at high temperatures. Previous studies have shown that particulate- and whisker-reinforced metal-matrix composites (MMC) present better strength and creep resistance [1-2] as well as wear resistance [3] at elevated temperatures than the corresponding unreinforced alloys. Additional advantages include the high stiffness and strength at ambient temperature, and the ability of being processed and machined by procedures similar to those employed for the monolithic alloys. The main drawback of these materials is their limited ductility and crack growth resistance, and most of the research activity has been directed to a study of these properties under various loading conditions and environments.

The combination of high specific strength and stiffness as well as wear resistance at elevated temperature offers a good potential for using these materials in structural applications designed to resist impact loading, dynamic penetration, or other dynamic loading conditions. However, the study of their dynamic mechanical properties has received very little attention in the past, and to the authors' knowledge only a few studies are available [4-6]. These were aimed at elucidating the behaviour in tension and fracture at room temperature, and the results were very encouraging. For instance, it was reported that tensile ductility and fracture toughness increase with the strain rate [4-5]. Fracture toughness also improved with temperature at high strain rates [6], although the temperature range studied was only from -196° to 100° C. The present study was designed to pursue these investigations by analyzing the effect of temperature (in the range 25 to 350° C) on the high strain rate tensile properties and failure mechanisms in a 2618 Al alloy reinforced with 15 vol. % SiC particulates. Tests were carried out in a split Hopkinson bar equipped with a furnace to control the temperature of the specimen, and the broken samples were examined with a scanning electron microscope to identify the dominant failure mechanisms. The results are discussed and compared with those obtained at room temperature under quasi-static loading conditions to reach a better understanding of the deformation and failure processes at high strain rates.

2. MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

A spray formed 2618 Al alloy reinforced with 15 vol. % of SiC particulates was used in this investigation. The nominal chemical composition of the alloy by weight was: Cu 2.3%, Mg 1.6%, Fe 1.1%, Ni 1.0%, Si 0.18%, balance Al. The Fe and Ni are added to enhance the microstructural stability under thermal exposure. The material was supplied by Cospray (Alcan Int. Ltd.) in the form of extruded rectangular bars. After extrusion, the bars were solution heat treated at 530°C for 1 hour, water quenched, and cold stretched up to 2% to relieve the residual stresses introduced by quenching. They were then artificially aged at 190°C during 10 hours to reach the peak-aged condition (T651), and tensile specimens were machined from the bars. Several specimens were then solution heat treated (1 hour at 530°C) to erase the effect of the prior thermo-mechanical treatments, quenched in water, and aged at room temperature during one week (T4).

Metallographic samples in the longitudinal direction were prepared following the procedures described in [7] to measure the relevant microstructural parameters. The grains were equiaxed (Figure 1) with an average grain size of 15 μm . Rounded inclusions, with an average size around 3 μm , were distributed within the Al alloy grains, at the grain boundaries, and at the SiC interfaces. Energy dispersive X-ray microanalysis and X-ray diffraction confirmed that the inclusions were made up of a monoclinic Al_9NiFe intermetallic [7]. Transmission electron microscopy studies detected the presence of S and S' precipitates (Al_2CuMg) in the peak-aged condition but not in the naturally aged material. The S' precipitates exhibited lath shapes and were distributed throughout the matrix. The S precipitates, on the other hand, were found mainly at the grain boundaries and at the SiC/matrix interfaces as well as at the Al_9NiFe /matrix interfaces. The SiC particulates exhibited an aspect ratio near to 2, with the longer axis oriented in the extrusion direction, and the shorter in the perpendicular one. The maximum and minimum dimensions of the reinforcement in the longitudinal direction were respectively $10.6 \pm 7.2 \mu\text{m}$ and $5.4 \pm 3.0 \mu\text{m}$.

Figure 1. Etched microstructure. The extrusion axis is horizontal. Al_9NiFe intermetallic inclusions are observed as small, rounded black dots. SiC particulates exhibit a light grey colour, and can be recognized by their larger size and elongated shape.

The tensile tests at high strain rate were carried out in a split Hopkinson bar. The experimental set-up is well known [8], and is not detailed here. Basically, the ends of the rounded tensile specimen (machined in the extrusion direction with 13 mm in gage length and 6 mm in diameter) were threaded to two high-strength steel bars. A tension pulse was generated at the other extreme of the striker bar, by impact of a tubular projectile, and it was partially transmitted to the second bar through the specimen. The bars remained in elastic regime during the test, and were instrumented with strain gauges. The force acting on the second bar was calculated from the strain gauge measurements and the elastic properties of the bar.

The stress in the specimen was obtained as the force transmitted to the second bar divided by the specimen section. The apparent strain in the specimen was obtained as the relative displacement between the bars divided by the gage length. This method assumes that the strain distribution is homogeneous throughout the specimen during the test. Detailed numerical and experimental analyses [9] have shown that this hypothesis is valid only in the central region of the specimen during plastic deformation, and that the actual plastic strains in this region are larger than the apparent strains measured as indicated above.

In the high temperature tests, the specimen was placed in an electric resistance furnace. The specimen temperature was measured with chromel-alumel thermocouples (accuracy $\pm 1\%$), and the heating rate was approximately 12°C per minute. Once the test temperature was attained, the specimens were held 20 minutes prior to testing to ensure a homogeneous temperature distribution through the specimen.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The ambient temperature quasi-static ($\dot{\epsilon} \approx 10^{-3} \text{ sec}^{-1}$) tensile behaviour of these materials was previously measured [7], and the results are compared in Table 1 with those obtained in the split-Hopkinson bar. Each value is the average of two tests. The only noticeable effect of the strain rate was to increase the ductility, whereas the tensile strength, σ_u , was not influenced despite the six orders of magnitude gap in $\dot{\epsilon}$. It is worth noting that the strain measurement system employed in the split Hopkinson bar underestimates the plastic strains in the central part of the specimen, and the differences in the ductility between low and high strain rates are actually larger than the figures in Table 1. This was in agreement with the results found in the literature, which indicated that the strain rate sensitivity of Al-based MMC at ambient temperature is very low in tension [4] and torsion [5], although the ductility increases with the strain rate. In this respect, discontinuously-reinforced Al-based composites behave like the corresponding Al matrices, which also present low strain rate sensitivity and an improvement in ductility at high strain rates [5, 10]

Table 1. Influence of the strain rate on the ambient temperature mechanical properties

Temper	$\dot{\epsilon}$ sec ⁻¹	σ_y (MPa)	σ_u (MPa)	ϵ_u (%)
T4	10^{-3}	254	482	12.3
T4	10^3	328	497	15.1
T651	10^{-3}	484	503	4.1
T651	10^3	488	524	8.5

The evolution with the temperature of yield strength (σ_y), tensile strength (σ_u) and apparent strain at maximum load ($\epsilon_{u,app}$) is shown respectively in Figs. 2, 3, and 4, for both tempers. The three magnitudes tended to decrease as the temperature increased, the only exception being the test carried out in the T651 temper at 100°C , which gave the peak values in σ_y and $\epsilon_{u,app}$ in the peak-aged condition over the temperature range studied. The drop in yield strength between ambient temperature and 350°C was moderate (13% in the T651 temper and 14% in the T4) and a similar result was obtained for the apparent strain at maximum load (18% and 13% reduction, respectively, in the T651 and T4 tempers). The tensile strength was only slightly influenced by the temperature in the T651 condition (13% reduction between 25 and 350°C) but this was not the case in the T4 temper, where σ_u at 350°C was 30% lower than at ambient temperature. The tensile strength of a 6061-T6 Al alloy tested between 25 and 345°C in a split Hopkinson bar [11] is also presented in Figure 3 for comparison purposes. The degradation of the mechanical properties above 200°C is much more marked in this material than in the composites. Similar results have been reported in [12] for a high strength 7075-T73 Al alloy tested in compression.

Figure 2. Yield strength (σ_y) as a function of the temperature at high strain rates.

Figure 3. Tensile strength (σ_u) as a function of the temperature at high strain rates. The behaviour of a 6061 Al alloy [11] under similar conditions is also plotted for comparison.

The fracture surfaces of the composites tested in the T651 condition at 25°C are shown in Figure 5a and at 350°C in Fig. 5b. They exhibit microscopically a ductile appearance, with voids around the SiC particulates and the intermetallic inclusions. Most of the SiC particulates showed a clean fracture and were well bonded to the matrix, which underwent extensive plastic deformation (Fig. 5c). Interfacial debonding did not seem to play an important role in the composite failure. One of the advantages of the spray forming method

Figure 4. Apparent strain at maximum load ($\epsilon_{u,app}$) as a function of the temperature at high strain rates.

is the rapid solidification of the material, which avoids segregation at the particulate-matrix interfaces, and leads to high interfacial strength. No significant differences were found on the fracture surfaces between the T651 and T4 tempers, and for brevity micrographs of the latter are not shown.

The results of the mechanical tests indicate that the strain rate did not greatly influence the tensile strength of MMC at ambient temperature, in agreement with previous observations [4-5], so it is reasonable to assume that the specific strengthening mechanisms which are operative under quasi-static loading conditions were maintained at high strain rates. These mechanisms included the load transfer from the matrix to the reinforcement, and the build-up of hydrostatic stresses in the matrix due to the reinforcement constraint to plastic flow [7] and in principle both are independent of the strain rate. Another strengthening source in the case of the T4 temper (where precipitates were not present) is the enhanced dislocation density in the matrix. Dislocations are emitted from the SiC/particulate interface upon cooling due to the mismatch in the thermal expansion coefficient between Al and SiC, and the raised composite yield strength is due to the entanglement of dislocations during deformation. As dislocation movement is a viscous process, the strengthening provided by this mechanism is expected to increase with the strain rate. This could explain the moderate improvement in the yield strength in the naturally aged composite between low and high strain rates.

Most significant was the twofold increase in ductility at ambient temperature in the T651 temper between the specimens tested at low and high strain rates. This increase was accompanied by substantial changes in the fracture surfaces, where a higher number of SiC particulates was seen in the materials tested under quasi-static loading conditions (Figure 6). When Figures 5 and 6 are compared, it is readily concluded that the dominant failure mechanism moved from reinforcement fracture at low strain rates to matrix cavitation at high strain rates. The increase in ductility with the strain rate was more moderate in the T4 temper, very likely because the area fraction of broken particulates found in the specimens tested under quasi-static loading was lower than in the T651 temper (Figure 7) [7]. Thus the change in the failure mechanism with the strain rate is less severe for the naturally aged material.

Figure 5. Fracture surfaces of the composites tested at high strain rates. (a) T651 temper, 25^oC. (b) T651 temper, 350^oC. (c) T4 temper, 25^oC.

Figure 6. Fracture surface of the composite tested under quasi-static loading conditions in the T651 temper. Many SiC particulates are observed in the micrograph.

The strength retention at high temperatures and high strain rates of this MMC was remarkable, especially when compared with other Al alloys tested under the same conditions [11-12]. However, the ultimate origin of this excellent behaviour is not well understood, and more research is needed to ascertain the main strengthening mechanisms. Further work, involving the unreinforced monolithic alloy processed by the same method, is being carried out.

Figure 7. Fracture surface of the composite tested under quasi-static loading conditions in the T4 temper.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The mechanical properties of a 2618 Al alloy reinforced with 15 vol. % SiC were measured at high strain rates in the temperature range 25^o to 350^oC. Yield strength, tensile strength and ductility decreased with the temperature, although the reduction in all these magnitudes was moderate. The good strength retention at elevated temperatures and high strain rate, together with the excellent wear resistance at high temperatures, give these materials a good potential for use in applications involving dynamic penetration and impact.

Comparison with the mechanical properties obtained at ambient temperature under quasi-static loading indicated that the strain rate sensitivity of this material was low. On the contrary, the ductility at high strain rates was significantly higher than under quasi-static loading conditions. Fractographic observations showed a change in the failure mechanisms with the strain rate. Fracture took place by reinforcement fracture at low strain rates (especially in the peak-aged condition), whereas matrix failure was dominant at high strain rates.

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